

Nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from high yield rice variety with site specific nutrient management in rainfed

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ABSTRACT

Indonesian government efforts to realize the sustainable food self-sufficiency is through rice cultivation on rainfed area. Rice cultivation used high yield rice variety and site specific nutrient management (SSNM) aim to improve fertilizer efficiency and reduce N₂O emission from rainfed area. The study was conducted on growing season 2015-2016 at Research Station of Indonesian Agriculture Environment Research Institute with rice varieties and fertilization treatments. Five rice varieties were used for this study, namely Inpago 8, Towuti, Batutegi, Inpari 14 and Situ Bagendit as control. Fertilization using SSNM based on Permentan No. 40/OT.140/4/2007 and the existing farmers. Dosage of fertilizer used by district of Jaken Pati is organic fertilizer (manure) 2 ton/ha, Urea 325 kg/ha, SP-36 50 kg/ha, KCl 30 kg/ha. Dosage of fertilizer existing of farmers use manure 4 ton/ha, Urea 250 kg/ha, SP-36 100 kg/ha and KCl 100 kg/ha. The results showed that Situ Bagendit variety in SSNM produced the lowest N₂O emissions (0.88 kg/ha/season).

Keywords : *emission, variety, fertilization, rainfed*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change as a result of global warming has been ongoing on the earth, and this is a serious threat to the agricultural sector. Climate change occurs due to an increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. The negative effects of climate change include drought, floods and pest attacks. One of the gases from rice fields that contribute to GHG emissions is N₂O, although the contribution of N₂O gas to the atmosphere is low (6% of the total greenhouse effect) but N₂O gas has a very stable nature and has a long residence time of up to 150 years (Balitbangtan, 2014). The agricultural sector contributes to N₂O emissions by 79% of the total national N₂O emissions (SNC, 2010). Therefore, it is necessary to mitigate N₂O by using balanced between inorganic and organic fertilizers and the selection of high yield rice variety.

Fertilization recommendations on rice cultivation are generally inefficient because of differences in soil fertility and nutrition requirements between locations. Therefore, in determining fertilizer dosage in rice cultivation

in a region has its own considerations. One way to save fertilization that can still increase rice productivity and maintain environmental sustainability is by site specific nutrient management (SSNM). SSNM is a technological innovation developed by the International Rice Research Institute, Indonesian Center for Food Crops Research and Development, Indonesian Center for Rice Research and Indonesian Agency for Agricultural Research and Development which contains guidelines for determining recommendations for fertilizing irrigated and rainfed lowland rice plants (Faroka, 2013; Pudjianto, 2016). According to Zaini (2012), one of the benefits of SSNM technology is to provide an efficient fertilization strategy (type, dosage and time application). Utilization of SSNM technology is expected to use N fertilizer can be more efficient and also can reduce N₂O emissions without ignoring the increase in production, farmer income and environmental sustainability.

At present, the production of rice produced is still unable to national needs, especially reaching the food self-sufficiency target. To achieve food self-sufficiency, it is necessary to adapt the technology, namely high yield rice variety and management of site specific nutrient. According to Adisarwanto et al., (2007), besides having high productivity, high yield rice variety is an easy and inexpensive technology for farmers. This study aims to determine the N₂O emissions in rice cultivation used high yield rice variety and management of site specific nutrient.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted on growing season 2015-2016 at Research Station of Indonesian Agriculture Environment Research Institute (IAERI) located at Jaken, Pati, Central Java. The study locations included lowland with an altitude of ± 7 m mean sea level. According the soil taxonomy the soil type in locations was inceptisols. The experimental design was a Randomized Block Design (RBD), with a plot area of 11 x 10 m. The experiment used two treatments, namely fertilization and rice varieties. Fertilization using SSNM based on Permentan No. 40/OT.140/4/2007 and the existing farmers. Dosage of fertilizer used by district of Jaken Pati is organic fertilizer (manure) 2 ton/ha, Urea 325 kg/ha, SP-36 50 kg/ha, KCl 30 kg/ha. Dosage of fertilizer existing farmers use manure 4 ton/ha, Urea 250 kg/ha, SP-36 100 kg/ha and KCl 100 kg/ha. Rice varieties were used for this study, namely Inpago 8, Towuti, Batutegi, Inpari 14 and Situ Bagendit as control. Seeds planted using rice seeder with jajar legowo 2:1 (20 x 10 x 40 cm). Before the seeds are planted, deep tillage is done by using a tractor. Irrigation comes from rainfall, while pest control is adjusted to field conditions.

Gas samples were measured using close chamber method. Gases were taken on interval time of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 minute after closing chamber. The size of chamber was 30 x 40 x 50 cm. N₂O concentration in the gas samples was estimated using a Gas Chromatography (GC Shimadzu 14A) equipped by *Electron Capture Detector* (ECD). The N₂O emissions was calculated using the following equation (IAEA, 1993):

$$E = \frac{dc}{dt} \times \frac{V_{ch}}{A_{ch}} \times \frac{mW}{mV} \times \frac{273.2}{(273.2 + T)}$$

Where :

- E : N₂O emissions (kg/ha/season)
- dc/dt : difference of gases concentration per time (ppm/minute)
- V_{ch} : volume of chamber (m³)
- A_{ch} : area of chamber (m²)
- mW : weight of gases molecule N₂O (g)
- mV : volume of gases molecule N₂O (22,4 l)
- T : average of temperature during gases sampling (°C)

Parameters recorded were soil pH, number of tillers, biomass, heavy 1000 grain and grain yield. ANOVA was used to calculate plant parameter, Tukey's (p < 0.05) was done to find out the differences between the recorded parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The N₂O fluxes were determined from 29 until 85 day after transplanting (DAT). The N₂O emissions in all the treatments were very diverse. The N₂O emissions among the rice varieties were around 0.88-2.98 kg/ha/season (Fig. 1). Situ Bagendit variety in SSNM produced the lowest N₂O emissions, while Inpari 14 variety in existing farmers produced the highest N₂O emissions. The N₂O emissions from Inpago 8, Towuti, Batutegi, Inpari 14 and Situ Bagendit in SSNM were 1.81; 1.22; 1.37; 1.51; 0.88 kg/ha/season respectively. The N₂O emissions from Inpago 8, Towuti, Batutegi, Inpari 14 and Situ Bagendit in existing farmers were 1.78; 1.14; 1.74; 2.98; 1.07 kg/ha/season respectively. The agriculture sector was responsible for about 87.2% of N₂O emissions, mainly from animal waste management and agricultural soils (Cerri et al., 2009). The main sources of N₂O are the application of N-fertilizer on soil, fossil fuel combustion and some natural mechanisms that occur in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. The annual increase rate varies from 0.2 to 0.3% (Signor and Cerri, 2013).

Figure 1. The total N₂O emissions among rice varieties

Most of the N₂O is produced through the biological processes of nitrification and denitrification. Soil temperature, soil moisture, soil pH are of great importance for nitrification and denitrification, because they determinate the activity of microorganism (Davidson and Swank, 1986). Measurement of soil pH and GHG sampling were carried out simultaneously. In this study, soil pH was relatively low (4.88-5.30). The lowest soil pH was found in Towuti variety with existing farmers, while the highest soil pH was found in Inpago 8 variety with SSNM. According to Simek and Cooper (2002), low soil pH decreases denitrification rates, but simultaneously the contribution of N₂O production to total nitrogenous gas production by denitrification is increased.

Figure 2. Soil pH during the growth period

Emissions and production are two things that are closely interrelated in efforts to adaptation and mitigation GHG emissions. Good agricultural practices should be applied to increase rice production and to promote environmental friendly agriculture system. Therefore, the information of productivity from high yield rice varieties and N₂O emission are needed on rice cultivation.

Table 1. Yield component among rice varieties

Varieties	SSNM				Existing Farmers			
	Number of tiller	Biomassa (g)	Heavy 1000 grain (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Number of tiller	Biomassa (g)	Heavy 1000 grain (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<u>Inpago 8</u>	39	108	32.2	5.39	67	134	32.1	5.94
<u>Towuti</u>	72	94	30.9	4.84	80	106	29.6	3.96
<u>Batutege</u>	39	183	27.4	5.99	47	134	26.7	7.19
<u>Inpari 14</u>	56	91	27.6	4.19	67	83	29.5	4.16
<u>Situ Bagendit</u>	72	120	29.2	5.09	70	133	30.0	3.75

Data describing the yield component among rice varieties are presented in Table 1. The number of tillers from five varieties in the generative phase is very diverse. The highest number of tillers was found in Towuti variety with existing farmers (80 tillers), while the lowest number of tillers was found in Inpago 8 and Batutege variety with SSNM 39 tillers respectively. The difference in number of tillers is caused by genotype and environmental factors (Suyanto et al., 2015). These factors are the cause of differences in rice yields. The number of tillers at generative phase has a direct effect on rice yield, the excessive and ineffective number of tillers makes plants inefficient in producing grain. The grain yield was maximum in Batutege using existing farmers fertilization (7.19 t/ha) and minimum in Towuti using existing farmers fertilization (3.96 t/ha).

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study showed that Situ Bagendit variety in site specific nutrient management (SSNM) produced the lowest N₂O emissions (0.88 kg/ha/season) and Inpari 14 variety in existing farmers produced the highest N₂O emissions (2.98 kg/ha/season).

REFERENCES

Adisarwanto, T., Subandi, dan Sudaryono. 2007. Teknologi produksi kedelai. Kedelai Teknik Produksi dan Pengembangan. Badan Penelitian dan

- Pengembangan Pertanian. Pusat Penelitian dan Pengembangan Tanaman Pangan.
Balitbangtan, 2014. Pedoman umum pengembangan model pertanian ramah lingkungan berkelanjutan. Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Pertanian. Kementerian Pertanian.
- Cerri, C.C., S.M.F. Maia., M.V. Galdos., C.E.P. Cerri., B.J. Feig and M. Bernoux. 2009. Brazilian greenhouse gases emissions : the importance of agriculture and livestock. *Scientia Agricola, Piracicaba.*, **66**(6):831-843.
- Davidson, E.A. and W.T. Swank. 1986. Environmental parameters regulating gaseous nitrogen losses from 2 forested ecosystem via nitrification and denitrification. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology, Baltimore.*, **52**(6):1287-1292.
- Faroka, F.R., K.B. Seminar, and P. Muljono, 2013. Pengaruh adopsi teknologi PHSL (pemupukan hara spesifik lokasi) berbasis pertanian presisi terhadap pendapatan petani padi di desa Jembungan, Kabupaten Boyolali Jawa Tengah. *Jurnal Komunikasi Pembanguna.n*, ISSN **11**(1):1693-3699.
- Pudjianto, T. 2016. Pemupukan Hara Spesifik Lokasi (PHSL) dengan HP. Agritani. <http://agri-tani.blogspot.com/2016/01/pemupukan-hara-spesifik-lokasi-phsl.html>. (Accesed 14 January 2017).
- Signor, D., and C.E.P. Cerri. 2013. Nitrous oxide emissions in agricultural soils : a review. E-ISSN 1983-4063. *Pesq. Agropec. Trop. Goiania.*, **43**(3):322-338.
- Simek, M and J.E. Cooper. 2002. The influence of soil pH on denitrification: progress towards the understanding of this interaction over the last 50 years. *European Journal of Soil Science.*, **53**:345-354.
- SNC, 2010. Second National Communication under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. UNFCC.
- Suyamto, M. Saeri, D.P. Saraswati dan Robi'in. (2015). Verifikasi dosis rekomendasi pemupukan hara Spesifik lokasi untuk padi varietas hibrida. *Penelitian Pertanian Tanaman Pangan.*, **34**(3):165-173.
- Zaini, Z. 2012. Pupuk majemuk dan pemupukan hara spesifik lokasi pada padi sawah. *Iptek Tanaman Pangan.*, **7**(1).